

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: SENGRETSI****FIRST NAME: LISA****PROGRAM CODE: LLM****COURSE CODE : ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)The author used the following software: MSWord 2016 on Windows 10

GUIDELINES FOR ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic writing has always been a challenging task for me. The process of brainstorming and research, accompanied by the need to meet a set of expectations spelt out by an instructor were exacting for me at the undergraduate level. I would say that the unavailability of a single document containing all the university's guidelines and requirements for academic papers contributed to this difficulty. This is not to say that my essays were poor or that I had no help from the university with regards to scholarly writing; but to show that the absence of a document containing most of the recommendations for an acceptable intellectual paper, affected the quality of work I produced. Thus, the ACA401 coursepack for period one provides relief since it clearly specifies what instructors expect to find in submitted assignments. Apart from the ACA-401 resource which is a selection of relevant articles, there is a tutorial video which gives students practical knowledge on how to edit and format the templates for response papers in Microsoft Word as well as direction on style guides. The ACA-401 course material for the first period of study will be a useful tool for me throughout my education at EUCLID and I will attempt to analyse it in this response paper.

2) BODY

a) Academic Essay Writing

The coursepack starts by giving information on the basics of academic essay writing and one of the tips given for successful writing is to start early (EUCLID 2019, 1).

I believe that this piece of advice cannot be overemphasized. I noticed during my undergraduate education that many students ended up plagiarizing on assignments because they began working only when submission dates were close. Beginning an assignment when the deadline is quite far gives a writer enough freedom to write and rewrite essays. With enough time on hand, the writer is able to review his or her work effectively, correcting overlooked mistakes and infusing new ideas to better support arguments. I realized that anytime I waited until deadlines were imminent to start my papers, there was additional pressure and this reduced my ability to submit assignments I was completely proud of. In some of these instances, I almost plagiarized because I did not have enough time to revise drafts of my work. I recognize that passing off someone's work as mine is an unforgivable academic offense and the coursepack has shown exactly how this pitfall can be avoided (EUCLID 2019, 5 – 12).

Apart from ensuring that my essays duly acknowledge the sources of information I use, there are certain pointers I should follow in order to make my work easy to read. The aim of academic essays is to persuade readers of an idea based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1). The use of the word 'persuade' tells me that academic essay writing involves more than just stating facts. It suggests to me that scholarly works are art masterpieces that should carry the reader along i.e. the reader should be able to follow a logical pattern of reasoning as he or she peruses the essay. While the process of reading typically follows a linear sequence of events, the process of writing does not have to follow the same pattern. Writers have the freedom to work on different parts of their essays at a time however, the final product is a work of art that uses a logical sequence of events and arguments to convince its end users about an issue. A piece of advice which is worthy of note is that "writing that does not sound right will not read right" (EUCLID 2019, 16). This is a useful guide for writers. As an academic writer, this will help me go about my work with the realization that the end user who is the reader should be able to read with ease.

b) Style Guides

Until I read the ACA-401 coursepack I did not know what a style guide was. I assumed that an essay was good enough if it was well cited and argued its points logically however, my interaction with the resource has broadened my knowledge. I am now aware of what a style guide is and why it is necessary to use one. "A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent" (EUCLID 2019, 24). A style guide enables the writer's work to have consistency in aspects like depth of treatment of a subject, the use of fonts, use of abbreviations, use of symbols, spelling etc (EUCLID 2019, 24 – 25). EUCLID recommends the Turabian style guide but accepts other internationally recognized styles (EUCLID 2019, 24). In the tutorial video provided for this study period, the style guide for University of Oxford was mentioned so I downloaded it in order to compare it to the Turabian style. I did this comparison to determine which style will be more suitable for me. The information on style guides is quite new to me so it was challenging for me to remember all the rules associated with each style guide. Thankfully, the material is readily available for me to refer to whenever I need it and by interacting with the resource frequently, I will be able to familiarize myself with a particular style guide.

c) American English vs. British English

I am Ghanaian and Ghana was colonized by Great Britain. Thus, throughout my education there has been an emphasis on speaking and writing Standard British English (SBE). This is what is required of a Ghanaian student and I assumed that I spoke the Queen's language with precision because I had good grades on my essays. However, my interaction with the coursepack brought to my understanding the fact that I, along with many other people in my country had been greatly influenced by American English. A sentence like "Have you got your grade in history yet?" (EUCLID 2019, 30) which is correct according to Great Britain's English standards would be considered as wrong in Ghana even though it is claimed that SBE is the language spoken in Ghana. Other American terms have seeped into Ghanaian speech to the extent that it is hard to tell whether it is British English or American English being spoken. American English has truly gained more relevance worldwide (EUCLID 2019, 27). After reviewing the differences between the two strands of English provided in the course material, I could not tell whether I spoke British English or American English. I initially assumed that I spoke British English but after examining some differences between the two versions, I am not sure if I have met the standards for either. Luckily for me, I have been given this resource which has broadened my knowledge scope. Armed with this new information, I can write better essays which will conform to accepted standards of one strand; Standard British English.

3) CONCLUSION

It is interesting to me that I am learning new things about a language I have been speaking all my life. Certain pieces of information I found in the coursepack were interesting to me. Notable among these was being told that I could speak in the first person singular (EUCLID 2019, 16). This idea sounded foreign to me; totally contradictory to what I heard all my life, but it also gave me some respite knowing that I could write my papers following my thought patterns and not having to convert all my thoughts into sentences that sound 'academic'. Nonetheless, I also acknowledge the fact that there should be a balance between my personal and academic style (EUCLID 2019, 12). Even though I have the liberty to use the first person singular, my essays should not take an entirely personal tone. My papers should still remain as academic as possible but have my personal style flowing through them. I found the information provided in the CMS Crib Sheet extremely useful and I will definitely refer to it when writing my subsequent papers (EUCLID 2019, 44 – 55). The use of style guides is uncharted territory for me and I must admit that I have some fears about whether or not I will be able to do that effectively. Nevertheless, I realize that taking a new path is generally challenging. Taking the decision to study at EUCLID was a tough one because I was unsure about what to expect. However, I know that if I take things one day at a time, I will be able to surmount any challenge I will face. Using a style guide seemed perplexing on first try but I know that with constant practice I will be able to perform better. As I take things one step at a time with the help of the resources made available to me, I am convinced that I will do excellently well.

WORKS CITED

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma, 2nd ed. 2019. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University.

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